

REGENERATIVE EXERGY RETURN ON INVESTMENT, A MORE ACCURATE INDICATOR OF AGRICULTURAL PROCESS EFFICIENCY.

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ABSTRACT

The exergy return on investment (EX_{ROI}) index, which represents the ratio between the non-renewable resources consumed by a system (exergetic cost) and the exergy contained in the product, has previously been used as a parameter to assess the efficiency of agricultural systems. In this work, the costs of agricultural soil regeneration are incorporated into the index, giving rise to $EX_{ROI}^{regenerative}$. Considering the costs associated with soil regeneration is essential to maintaining soil quality and workability in the long term, as it accounts for the replenishment of nutrients, organic matter, and other parameters typically degraded in agricultural processes. Thus, the $EX_{ROI}^{regenerative}$ index provides a more comprehensive measure of the efficiency and sustainability of farming systems, capturing not only immediate productivity but also the efforts required to mitigate environmental impacts and restore soil quality after harvest. This index has been calculated for field trials under different crops and conditions, and the results highlight the importance of including the exergy cost of soil regeneration as a key parameter for a holistic assessment of both the efficiency and long-term sustainability of cropping systems.

1 INTRODUCTION

Agricultural activities are essential for food production but also account for significant energy consumption. Detailed studies have estimated that open-field agriculture within the European Union (EU) requires at least 1435 petajoules (PJ) of energy, which corresponds to approximately 3.7% of the total energy consumption in the region (Paris et al., 2022).

Another aspect directly related to agriculture that is often overlooked is soil. In Europe, between 60% and 70% of soils are considered to be in poor condition, posing a major challenge to sustainable food production and the ecosystem services essential for human well-being. The economic impact of soil degradation across the European Union is substantial, with annual costs exceeding €50 billion (European Commission, 2020). Since topsoil regenerates at an extremely slow rate, soil degradation is largely irreversible. This uppermost layer, which contains vital nutrients, organic matter, and biological activity, requires approximately 500 years to develop just 2.5 cm under agricultural conditions (Pimentel et al., 2010). Poorly managed intensive farming accelerates soil depletion, further worsening the issue. The decline in soil fertility caused by continuous cultivation does not become immediately evident in yield assessments but gradually affects future harvests. To compensate for these losses, farmers typically increase fertilizer use, which in turn drives up energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions.

The Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology is commonly used to analyze the environmental impacts of agriculture, including its energy consumption. However, LCA approaches do not consider soil quality and fertility, which can sometimes result in more favourable evaluations for intensive agricultural systems due to their higher yields per hectare (van der Werf et al., 2020). This limitation may place agroecological practices at a disadvantage in comparative studies, even though intensive

farming often depletes soil health in favour of short-term productivity. Nevertheless, conducting a comprehensive soil assessment remains challenging due to the complex interactions among physical, chemical, and biological factors (Bünemann et al., 2018).

Previous studies have introduced exergy as a valuable indicator for assessing soil systems (Palacino et al., 2022; Valero et al., 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022) and for quantifying the remediation efforts required to restore soil quality degraded by agricultural practices (Palacino, Ascaso, Valero, & Valero, 2024). This approach evaluates soil degradation and quality loss after crop production using the concept of exergy replacement cost. Soil fertility is often perceived as an inexhaustible natural resource; however, its depletion results in long-term efficiency losses and economic costs that are not always explicitly accounted for. To address this issue, exergy has been proposed as a means of estimating the energy required for soil regeneration. As a measure of the usable energy available in a system, exergy can be used to quantify the energy inputs necessary to restore soil fertility. This methodology considers key remediation processes, including nutrient replenishment, organic matter restoration, sodicity correction, and soil acidification mitigation.

This study aims to develop a comprehensive metric for evaluating the efficiency of agricultural systems. To achieve this, the exergy regeneration cost has been integrated into the Exergy Return on Investment (ExROI) index, leading to the formulation of the novel $ExROI_{REGENERATIVE}$ metric. Validation through field trial data will demonstrate the applicability of this approach and highlight the importance of incorporating soil regeneration into agricultural efficiency assessments.

2 METHODOLOGY

Building on the Energy Return on Investment (EROI) concept (Cleveland et al., 1984), Font de Mora et al. (Font de Mora et al., 2012) introduced the Exergy Return on Investment (ExROI) index to incorporate energy quality through exergy costs, initially applying it to biodiesel production. The ExROI index serves as a key metric for evaluating the exergy efficiency of industrial processes by comparing the exergy output generated to the exergy invested. A lower exergy investment cost for obtaining a given resource results in a higher ExROI value, indicating greater efficiency. While the ExROI index has primarily been applied to crops cultivated for biodiesel production, it can also serve as a broader measure of agricultural efficiency across various crop types (Eq. 1).

$$ExROI = \frac{\text{Exergy obtained}}{\text{Exergy invested}} = \frac{\text{Crop exergy}}{\text{Exergy cost of the agricultural process}} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

In this framework, the exergy output is equated to the High Heating Value (HHV) of the harvested biomass. By considering the HHV, it is possible to quantify the exergy extracted from the soil system and determine its potential use for energy production or food supply. The exergy input, on the other hand, is determined by accounting for all exergy expenditures associated with the agricultural process. This includes mechanical operations such as tillage, sowing, and harvesting, as well as irrigation activities and the production and distribution of fertilizers and other inputs. A methodologically rigorous approach for quantifying the exergy needed for executing these processes was developed in previous works (Palacino, Ascaso, Valero, Lima, et al., 2024)

The $ExROI_{REGENERATIVE}$ index (Eq. 2) is calculated by incorporating the exergy regeneration cost, which accounts for the exergy required to restore the soil to its original state. This is done by subtracting the exergy needed for soil restoration from the total exergy obtained from the crop. Unlike conventional efficiency metrics, this "net" exergy return not only evaluates the system's efficiency in crop production but also integrates the impact of agricultural practices on soil health. By considering the energy investment required to regenerate soil conditions, this metric provides a more comprehensive assessment of agricultural sustainability.

$$ExROI_{REGENERATIVE} = \frac{\text{Exergy obtained}}{\text{Exergy invested}} = \frac{\text{Crop exergy} - \text{Exergy regeneration cost}}{\text{Exergy cost of the agricultural process}} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

The regeneration cost allows to estimate the loss of soil fertility due to agricultural production through energy units. Four different terms are considered in the regeneration processes: nutrients, organic matter, salinity and acidification.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the parameters considered for calculating the exergy cost of regeneration (Palacino, Ascaso, Valero, & Valero, 2024).

Plant growth relies on the extraction of **nutrients** from the soil. In the absence of fertilization, the nutrient concentration in the soil may decline, potentially leading to problems with crop growth. Macronutrients, such as nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, calcium, and magnesium, are required in large quantities, while micronutrients like copper, iron, manganese, and zinc are essential in smaller amounts. Soil nutrient replacement can be achieved through the use of mineral, organic, or biological fertilizers and organic amendments. These processes incur a cost, which is associated with the energy required for the production, transport, and field distribution of fertilizers. In this methodology, the energy costs linked to nutrient depletion are quantified by considering the energy required to produce each nutrient in its inorganic form. An extensive literature review was conducted to compare and analyze various data sources to ensure accuracy, allowing the selection of the most representative values for each nutrient (Palacino, Ascaso, Valero, & Valero, 2024).

The following equation (Eq. (1)) should be used for the calculation of nutrient content needed for the quantity of amendment. Equation 2 should be applied to estimate the Nutrient Amendment (MJ/ha) based on the result of equation 1 and the fertiliser production cost (exergy, Table 1).

$$\text{Nutrient (kg/ha)} = \text{Variation content (kg Nutrient/kgsoil)} \cdot 10,000 \frac{\text{m}^2}{\text{ha}} \cdot 0.3\text{m} \cdot 1,400 \frac{\text{kgsoil}}{\text{m}^3} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Nutrient Amendment (MJ/ha)} = \text{Nutrient} \left(\frac{\text{kg Nut}}{\text{ha}} \right) \cdot \text{Fertilizer prod. Cost} \left(\frac{\text{MJ}}{\text{kg Nut}} \right) \quad (2)$$

Table 1: Data of exergy costs for each type of nutrient applied to the soil (Palacino, Ascaso, Valero, & Valero, 2024).

Nutrient	Exergy value	Units
Inorganic nitrogen	67.8	MJ/kg N
Phosphorus	50.87	MJ/kg P
Potassium	15.06	MJ/kg K
Calcium	22.89	MJ/kg Ca
Magnesium	31.2	MJ/kg Mg
Copper	222.94	MJ/kg Cu
Iron	9.25	MJ/kg Fe
Manganese	73.08	MJ/kg Mn
Zinc	28.77	MJ/kg Zn

Organic matter plays a critical role in soil, influencing numerous physical, chemical, and biological properties (Lal, 2016). The replenishment of organic matter in the soil will be evaluated based on replacement costs, which will consider the exergy required to restore a specific amount of organic matter in the soil, as well as the irreversibilities involved in the process. To estimate the energy involved in adding organic matter to the soil, composting was selected as a representative method for replenishing organic matter as it is the most appropriate and widely used treatment. However, organic matter applied to the soil undergoes decomposition, and only a portion is stabilized over the long term. Therefore, in addition to the exergetic cost of compost production, a soil incorporation factor was included. This factor represents the percentage of organic matter applied to the soil that decomposes and becomes part of the stable soil organic matter. Based on the studies by Lützow et al. (Lützow et al., 2006), the selected soil incorporation factor is 10%. This implies that to recover all the organic matter lost from the soil due to agricultural practices, an amendment 100 times greater than the required amount must be applied. **Sodicity** increases particularly in irrigation soils as irrigation water often contains salts that accumulate in the soil. Additionally, fertilizers further increase the salt concentration in the soil. Its regeneration was assumed with the addition of gypsum, one of the most common methods for remediating sodic soils. The exergy cost for gypsum was determined by considering the average primary energy required for both gypsum extraction and its production from flue gas desulfurization as sulfur and adding an extra 30% to account for incomplete reactivity (Weil & Brady, 2017).

For soil **acidity**, the typical remedy is to amend the soil with alkaline materials known as agricultural limes (Marschner, 2011; Weil & Brady, 2017). Based on estimates from Weil & Brady (2017) for various soil types, the required amount of ground limestone to raise the pH to 6.5 was calculated. The exergy cost for limestone was then determined according to its calcium content considering the average primary energy required to extract limestone as calcium (Ca).

3 RESULTS

For the real estimation of the variation of the parameters, an agricultural soil analysis, before and after the agricultural process and the harvesting of the crop is needed. This section compares the efficiency in terms of $ExROI_{REGENERATIVE}$ and $ExROI$ using real data obtained from field experiments. Two distinct fertilization strategies are applied, and the data on soil conditions prior to cultivation is used as the reference baseline.

Field trials were conducted over two consecutive growing seasons with wheat and triticale at the same experimental site in Gea de Albarracín, Spain. Two fertilization treatments were evaluated for both crops:

- Treatment 1: Basal fertilization with NPK (0-30-0) at a rate of 95 kg/ha, followed by topdressing with conventional urea at 150 kg/ha.
- Treatment 2: Basal fertilization with NPK (0-15-0) at 187.5 kg/ha, combined with topdressing using coated urea at 150 kg/ha.

The key differences between these treatments lie in the phosphorus concentration of the NPK fertilizer applied during basal fertilization and the type of urea used for topdressing. Treatment 1 utilizes a more concentrated but lower-dose phosphorus application, while Treatment 2 employs a higher overall phosphorus dosage. Additionally, the use of coated urea in Treatment 2 facilitates a slower and more controlled release of nitrogen into the soil, potentially influencing nutrient availability and crop performance.

In both cases, wheat was cultivated in the following growing season under identical conditions, except for basal fertilization, where an NPK formulation of 8-15-15 at 200 kg/ha was applied. These trials aimed to determine whether variations in phosphorus application rates and nitrogen release mechanisms impact overall crop efficiency and soil sustainability.

Table 2: Summary of parameters quantified from results obtained in the 8 agronomic trials

	Yield (t/ha)	Crop exergy (toe/ha)	Exergy cost of the agricultural process (toe/ha)	ExROI	Exergetic cost of regeneration (toe/ha)	ExROI _{REGENERATIVE}
TRITICALE PFC	3,75	1,56	0,22	7,06	0,64	4,16
TRITICALE PFI	6,62	2,75	0,22	12,39	0,002	12,38
WHEAT PFC	8,27	3,36	0,22	15,20	0,00	15,20
WHEAT PFI	6,47	2,62	0,22	11,80	0,00	11,80
WHEAT-TRITICALE PFC	7,79	3,40	0,27	12,59	2,90	1,85
WHEAT-TRITICALE PFI	8,18	3,24	0,27	12,00	1,65	5,89
WHEAT-WHEAT PFC	8,34	3,38	0,27	12,52	4,46	-4,00
WHEAT-WHEAT PFI	7,96	3,80	0,27	14,07	3,80	0,00

As shown in Table 2, crop yields exhibit only minor fluctuations in most cases, although some results fall significantly below the average. The costs associated with the agricultural process remain relatively consistent, with no significant differences observed between innovative and conventional treatments. However, notable variations emerge in the second season due to an increase in the base dressing dosage, which directly influences overall costs. Yield fluctuations, in turn, impact the ExROI indicator, the primary metric under evaluation. In field trials, these variations can be influenced by numerous factors, including climatic conditions, pest infestations, and disease outbreaks. As a result, drawing broad conclusions from single data points in each case study presents inherent limitations.

Wheat grown under conventional treatment (CBP) achieves an ExROI index of 15.20, indicating a high level of efficiency in terms of exergy. This value signifies that for every unit of energy invested in the agricultural process, 15.20 units of usable energy are generated through the crop. Such efficiency is comparable to the highest EROI values recorded for fossil fuels like oil and natural gas, which have a global average of approximately 20. The exceptional performance of wheat can be attributed to its relatively high yield (3.36 toe/ha) in relation to the modest energy costs of cultivation (0.221 toe/ha).

In contrast, triticale under the same treatment (PFC) registers the lowest ExROI index, with a value of 7.06. Despite agricultural process costs being similar to wheat, the triticale crop's exergy output is significantly lower (1.56 toe/ha), resulting in reduced overall efficiency for this particular crop. However, in the second season, the discrepancies between crops and treatments become less pronounced, as wheat yields remain relatively stable across different treatments. Although the PFI treatment demonstrates advantages in exergy efficiency for wheat-wheat rotations, its benefits are less evident in wheat-tritonal rotations, suggesting that treatment effectiveness may vary depending on crop type.

Figure 1: Comparison of the index ExROI and ExROI_{REGENERATIVE} obtained in the different field trials.

When the exergetic cost of regeneration is incorporated into the $ExROI_{REGENERATIVE}$ index, significant variations in results emerge (see Table 2 and Figure 1). During the first season, since wheat does not incur regeneration costs, the $ExROI_{REGENERATIVE}$ index closely mirrors the $ExROI$ index. However, an exception is observed in the trial involving triticale treated with PFC, where the $ExROI_{REGENERATIVE}$ index experiences a marked decline. This decrease suggests a greater inefficiency in the system.

In contrast, the second season reveals more pronounced discrepancies compared to the first. Notably, wheat following wheat, which was previously identified as highly efficient under PFI treatment, ranks among the least efficient scenarios once the exergetic costs of regeneration are accounted for. This shift occurs because the energy required to restore soil conditions after harvest surpasses the exergy gained from crop production, leading to a negative balance. These results show how the effects on the soil can lead to a loss of efficiency, which will not be noticeable at the end of the crop cycle but will become evident in the long term.

In the four crop cycles analyzed during the second harvest, a sharp decline in yield is observed when accounting for the cost of soil regeneration. Specifically, wheat after wheat emerges as the least efficient case, as the energy demand for both cultivation and soil restoration either matches or exceeds the exergy obtained from the yield. This holds true for both PFI and PFC treatments, reinforcing the inefficiency of this approach.

Overall, these findings underscore the importance of evaluating not only direct agricultural productivity but also the capacity for soil regeneration. Incorporating these factors is essential for maintaining the long-term efficiency of agricultural systems and ensuring the conservation and sustainability of soil resources.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The efficiency of crop production can be assessed using the ExROI index. However, as with many agricultural evaluation methods, overlooking soil fertility depletion and quality degradation as key factors may lead to misleading conclusions, particularly in the long term. To address this limitation, the ExROI_{REGENERATIVE} index incorporates the exergetic cost of soil regeneration alongside the energy output from crops and the exergy expenditures associated with the agricultural process. This approach provides a more comprehensive assessment of agricultural efficiency by accounting for both productive output and the resources required to restore soil conditions.

Field trial results reveal substantial differences in efficiency outcomes when soil regeneration and farming system sustainability are factored into the analysis. By integrating these considerations, the ExROI_{REGENERATIVE} index enables a broader understanding that extends beyond immediate productivity, encompassing the energy demands necessary to mitigate environmental impacts and restore soil quality after harvest. These findings highlight the importance of including soil exergy regeneration costs in agricultural efficiency evaluations, as neglecting this aspect can lead to an incomplete and potentially flawed assessment of long-term efficiency and sustainability.

Adopting such a holistic perspective fosters more informed and responsible agricultural management, striking a balance between maximizing yields and ensuring the preservation and restoration of soil resources. By offering a more accurate measure of sustainability, the ExROI_{REGENERATIVE} index serves as a valuable tool for guiding agricultural practices toward long-term viability and ecological resilience.

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